

Modelling fluid flow and water-rock interaction in fractured rocks using a Discrete Fracture Network approach: The case of barite vein formation.

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The migration of groundwater (and other types of fluids, in general) in fractured rocks allows the interaction between fluids in geochemical disequilibrium with the host rocks (i.e., large geochemical gradients) promoting water-rock reactions inside the fractures. These reactions may influence the permeability and porosity, as well as they may lead to fracture sealing. So, a thorough understanding of the coupled hydro-chemical processing that occur in fractured media is important for applications such as the ore deposit exploration, the protection and remediation of aquifers used for drinking water production or the safety assessment of deep geological repositories for spent nuclear fuel, energy storage, nuclear waste disposal sites.

In this contribution, geochemical reactions are being implemented in dfnWorks software to quantify the impact of geochemical reactions in a synthetic fracture network and compare the model results with natural examples. One of the potential impacts would be the modification of groundwater flow patterns due to mineral precipitation or dissolution. Also, the DFN-based reactive transport simulations also can help predict the effect of physical properties of the fractures, like aperture, and the chemical composition of the fluids on the reactive transport.

In this research, the model predictions have been made in a synthetic fracture network where two geochemically distinct fluids mix leading to the precipitation of barite. This is a common phenomenon observed in many fractured rocks undergoing extensional tectonics. The model results predict that barite precipitates in a main fault from the first fluid mixing and the precipitation keeps increasing there without a significant spreading to connected neighbour fractures. This agrees with observation in nature where barite precipitation is concentrated in few fracture veins within a large fracture network. The precipitation amounts and rate seemed to be sensitive to the reaction rate, fluids pressure gradient, and fracture aperture dimensions. While it showed no major sensitivity to the fluid temperature, all these factors were modelled under isothermal conditions and constant permeability. Further work will be focused on non-isothermal models, and precipitation pattern comparison with actual barite veins in the Catalan Coastal Ranges.

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